

TABLE 1—63/37 (3×6 cm) BRASS IN 0.5N ACETIC ACID WITH AROMATIC AMINES

Duration : 10 days

Concentration of inhibitor (%)	Loss (mdd)	Inhibition (%)	Concentration of inhibitor (%)	Loss (mdd)	Inhibition (%)
<i>Aniline</i>			<i>p-Anisidine</i>		
0.0	24.1		0.0	24.1	—
0.08	18.4	24	0.005	17.9	26
0.2	14.9	38	0.01	16.7	31
0.4	13.2	45	0.025	13.6	44
0.8	13.1	46	0.05	3.53	85
2.0	15.1	33	0.08	3.03	87
<i>o-Toluidine</i>			<i>p-Phenetidine</i>		
0.08	24.6	—2	0.08	1.97	92
0.2	23.6	2	0.2	1.88	92
0.4	22.8	6	0.4	2.27	91
0.8	21.2	12	0.8	2.58	89
1.9	5.3	78	2.1	3.22	87

In *o*-phenetidine oxygen and nitrogen atoms are attached to adjacent carbon atoms of the benzene ring. Both the atoms may be simultaneously adsorbed by the surface covering a much effective area compared to that covered by a single atom. *p*-Anisidine is a better inhibitor than aniline because of the fact that latter contains oxygen atom which can be more strongly adsorbed by metal surface than nitrogen atom. *o*-Toluidine contains methyl group adjacent to $-\text{NH}_2$. This methyl group acts as a steric hindrance to nitrogen atom being adsorbed to the metallic surface. This explains the poor inhibitive power of the substance.

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p-Substituted aromatic amines as corrosion inhibitors for 63/37 brass in nitric acid

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NITRIC acid is highly corrosive to copper and copper-zinc alloys. The corrosive attack of nitric acid on copper is mainly due to the nitrous acid formed during the reaction between copper and nitric acid. Therefore a substance which prevents the autocatalytic cycle of the formation of nitrous acid would act as a corrosion inhibitor. As aromatic amines can react with nitrous acid they should be able to retard the corrosion of copper and copper-zinc alloys in nitric acid. Orthosubstituted aromatic amines have been previously investigated as corrosion inhibitor for 63/37 brass in nitric acid¹. The present article reports the use of *p*-toluidine, *p*-anisidine and *p*-chloroaniline and *p*-aminobenzoic acid as corrosion inhibitors for 63/37 brass in nitric acid solutions.

Experimental

63/37 brass supplied by Messrs Kamani Metals, Bombay, was used for the study. The preparation of specimens and corrosion tests were carried out as described in earlier publication². The effect of inhibitor concentration and time on inhibitor efficiency is given in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. The change in potential with time of 63/37 brass in 2.0N

NOTES

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF INHIBITOR CONCENTRATION ON INHIBITOR EFFICIENCY

Inhibitor concentration	2.0N HNO ₃ 120 min.		3.0N HNO ₃ 60 min.		4.0N HNO ₃ 30 min.	
	loss mg/dm ²	% Efficiency	loss mg/dm ²	% Efficiency	loss mg/dm ²	% Efficiency
nil	1578.0	—	10676.0	—	13800.0	—
<i>p-toluidine</i>						
0.1%	429.0	72.8	1817.0	83.0	7756.0	43.8
0.2	209.9	86.7	741.5	93.1	4952.0	64.1
0.5	123.8	92.1	93.3	99.1	1005.2	92.7
1.0	30.8	97.6	38.8	99.6	100.8	99.3
<i>p-anisidine</i>						
0.01%	1271.0	19.41	5540.0	48.0	592.8	95.7
0.1	487.5	69.8	2247.0	79.0	576.2	95.8
0.2	76.7	95.1	546.4	94.9	380.4	97.2
0.5	10.2	99.4	182.8	98.3	63.4	99.6
<i>p-chloroaniline</i>						
0.01%	30.2	98.1	1432.6	86.6	9035.0	34.5
0.05	23.5	98.4	726.5	93.2	7409.0	46.37
0.1	24.9	98.4	252.3	97.7	1869.1	87.4
0.5	24.3	98.5	39.6	99.6	36.7	99.7
<i>p-aminobenzoic acid</i>						
0.025%	9.4	99.4	8.0	99.8	10492.5	24.0
0.05	9.4	99.4	5.8	99.8	5890.4	57.3
0.1	7.2	99.6	4.7	99.9	3531.5	74.4
0.5	4.1	99.7	3.0	99.9	1.4	99.9

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF TIME ON INHIBITOR EFFICIENCY

	loss	%								
	mg/dm ²	Effi- ciency								
2.0N HNO₃										
	15 min.		30 min.		60 min.		90 min.		120 min.	
nil	153.8	—	317.0	—	685.7	—	1116.0	—	1578.0	—
<i>p-toluidine</i> 1.0%	27.7	82.0	54.0	83.1	78.4	88.6	96.9	91.3	36.8	97.6
<i>p-anisidine</i> 0.2%	23.5	85.8	31.3	96.1	61.4	91.1	65.1	94.1	546.4	94.9
<i>p-chloroaniline</i> 0.5%	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	24.3	98.5
<i>p-aminobenzoic acid</i> 0.5%	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	2.0	99.9	4.1	99.7
3.0N HNO₃										
	5 min.		10 min.		15 min.		30 min.		60 min.	
nil	243.5	—	1039.0	—	1693.0	—	5097.0	—	10670.0	—
<i>p-toluidine</i> 1. %	22.1	90.9	38.8	96.2	60.9	96.4	78.4	98.4	38.8	99.6
<i>p-anisidine</i> 0.5%	16.6	92.9	21.6	97.9	33.8	97.9	91.4	98.2	182.8	98.3
<i>p-chloroaniline</i> 0.5 %	17.7	92.7	23.5	97.6	21.0	98.7	27.7	99.4	39.6	99.6
<i>p-aminobenzoic acid</i> 0.5%	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	3.0	99.9
4.0N HNO₃										
	2 min.		5 min.		10 min.		15 min.		30 min.	
nil	479.2	—	1592.0	—	4300.0	—	6794.0	—	13800.0	—
<i>p-toluidine</i> 1. %	44.3	88.8	83.1	94.8	86.1	98.0	90.4	98.6	100.8	99.3
<i>p-anisidine</i> 0.5%	9.	98.1	35.7	97.7	44.8	98.9	54.0	99.2	63.4	99.6
<i>p-chloroaniline</i> 0.5%	9.9	97.9	16.6	98.9	24.1	99.4	29.1	99.5	36.7	99.7
<i>p-aminobenzoic acid</i> 0.5%	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	1.4	99.9

nitric acid in the presence and absence of inhibitors is given in Figure 1. The effect of current density

Fig. 1. Change in potential of 63/37 brass with time in 2.0N nitric acid in the presence and absence of inhibitors

- — ● para aminobenzoic acid
- — □ para chloroaniline
- × — × para toluidine
- ▲ — ▲ para anisidine
- △ — △ uninhibited 2.0N HNO₃

on the cathode and anode potentials of 63/37 brass in 2.0N nitric acid is given in Figure 2.

Observations

The corrosion of 63/37 brass in nitric acid increases with time as well as with the concentration of nitric acid.

p-Toluidine

The efficiency of para toluidine improves with the passage of time. In the presence of *p*-toluidine, the potential values with time are negative than those in its absence indicating its action on the local cathodes. *p*-Toluidine acts as inhibitor by increasing the cathode polarisation. The anode polarisation is also increased to a certain extent.

p-Anisidine

A comparison of the results obtained with *p*-toluidine and *p*-anisidine shows that *p*-anisidine is a better inhibitor than *p*-toluidine. In the presence

of *p*-anisidine the potential values with time are more negative than those in its absence indicating the action of the inhibitor on local cathodes. *p*-Anisidine induces a considerable increase in the cathode polarisation. A comparison of shifts in the cathode potentials during cathode polarisation indicates that the

Fig. 2. Influence of current density on the cathode and anode potentials of 63/37 brass in 2.0N nitric acid in the presence and absence of inhibitors

- — ○ para aminobenzoic acid
- △ — △ para chloroaniline
- ▲ — ▲ para anisidine
- × — × para toluidine
- — ● uninhibited 2.0N nitric acid

shifts in presence of *p*-anisidine are more than those in presence of *p*-toluidine which confirms the better inhibitive action of *p*-anisidine.

p-Chloroaniline

In the presence of *p*-chloroaniline the potential values are negative than those in its absence indicating action of inhibitor on the local cathodes. Addition of *p*-chloroaniline induces a tremendous increase in cathode polarisation. The anode is also polarised to a certain extent.

p-Aminobenzoic acid

p-Aminobenzoic acid is a very good inhibitor for the corrosion of the 63/37 brass in nitric acid. It completely arrests the corrosion in 2N nitric acid upto 60 min, in 3N HNO₃ upto 30 min and in 4N HNO₃ upto 15 min. In the presence of *p*-aminobenzoic acid, the potential values with time are highly negative than those in its absence. Polarisation measurements indicate that the addition of *p*-aminobenzoic acid increases both the cathode and the anode polarisations.

All the substances act as inhibitors by removing nitrous acid formed during the reaction between brass and nitric acid. The order of efficiency is *p*-aminobenzoic acid > *p*-chloroaniline > *p*-toluidine > *p*-anisidine.

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A Rapid method for the gravimetric determination of Copper(II) in presence of Cadmium(II) by α -keto acid oxime

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QUANTITATIVE precipitation of copper by phenylpyruvic acid oxime has been reported by Katyal and Singh¹. It has been reported by the same authors² that in highly acidic medium (HNO_3) at 1-2 pH cadmium salt gives no precipitate with phenylpyruvic acid oxime and copper complex undergoes partial decomposition and hence separation of copper in presence of cadmium is not possible. It has been observed that in highly acidic medium (H_2SO_4) at pH 1-2 copper ion forms bluish copper complex with phenylpyruvic acid oxime while cadmium ion remains in the solution. By raising the pH of the solution upto 6-7, cadmium is precipitated as $\text{Cd}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{NO}_3)_2$ but as the complex is slightly soluble, no quantitative precipitation could be obtained and therefore cadmium is estimated as oxinate³.

Experimental

Standard Copper sulphate solution : To prepare the standard solution $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.9824 g.) of B.D.H. (A.R.) grade was dissolved in water, few drops of dilute sulphuric acid was added and the volume made 250 ml. The amount of copper was determined iodometrically⁴.

Standard Cadmium sulphate solution : The standard solution was prepared by dissolving $3\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (about 2.0 g.) in 250 ml water and cadmium was estimated as cadmium oxinate³ with 8-hydroxyquinoline.

Phenylpyruvic Acid Oxime : Phenylpyruvic acid was prepared from benzaldehyde via azalactone synthesis⁵. The acid (5.0 g.) was converted to its oxime by treating its solution in sodium hydroxide (70 ml, 10%) with aqueous solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (6.0 g. in 10 ml). The reaction mixture was kept overnight at room temperature and acidified

with hydrochloric acid to give the oxime, crystallising from benzene, m.p. 162°-63°. Hiromoto Ueda and Masaki Ohta⁶ reported its m.p. 160°-62°.

Procedure : A mixture of copper sulphate and cadmium sulphate solutions in different proportions was taken and the pH was adjusted to 1-2 by the addition of dilute sulphuric acid. An ethanolic solution of phenylpyruvic acid oxime (3%) was added to it. Copper was precipitated as copper phenylpyruvic acid oxime while cadmium ion remains in the solution.

The ligand solution was added dropwise till the precipitation was complete. The whole contents were heated on water bath for 15 min and filtered through a weighed sintered glass crucible. The precipitate was washed several times with hot water to remove sulphate ion and finally with alcohol to remove the excess of the ligand. It was dried at 110.20° for 45 min in an air oven, cooled in a desiccator and weighed as $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{NO}_3)_2$ to a constant weight.

The filtrate with washings were collected and evaporated to dryness with conc. nitric acid till the residue became colourless (3-4 times required). Finally it was evaporated with dilute nitric acid and the solution was made in water. Cadmium was estimated as cadmium oxinate³ by the help of 8-hydroxyquinoline.

Results

Metals present in mixture in mg		Metals estimated in mg		% Error	
Cu	Cd	Cu	Cd	Cu	Cd
1.0296	100.84	1.0298	101.065	0.02	0.23
		1.0298	101.12	0.02	0.28
5.148	80.672	5.149	80.684	0.02	0.015
		5.119	80.627	0.56	0.055
10.296	60.504	10.268	60.414	0.27	0.15
		10.298	60.471	0.02	0.05
25.739	40.338	25.685	40.314	0.21	0.06
		25.716	40.426	0.09	0.22
51.478	20.168	51.594	20.156	0.23	0.06
		51.618	20.213	0.27	0.22

The above experimental results indicate that even a small amount of copper present in the mixture of copper and cadmium salts solution can be successfully separated and estimated. If the amount of copper or cadmium is varied, the separation and estimation can be done with equal efficiency.

The thermogravimetric study of the complexes shows that both copper and cadmium complexes are quite stable upto 140°.

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